

Grant Agreement No: 861198
Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action (MSCA) Innovative Training Network (ITN)

TECHNICAL DESIGN REPORT

OPTIMUM FILAMENT SETUP FOR EFFICIENT LR EVAPORATION

Milestone: MS21

Document identifier:	LISA-Dx.x-Title-VX
Due date of deliverable:	End of Month 12 (November 2020)
Justification for delay:	Delayed availability of template
Report release date:	dd/mm/yyyy
Work package:	WP5: Exploring the limits of nuclear existence
Lead beneficiary:	GSI Helmholtz centre for heavy ion research
Document status:	Draft [Final when fully approved]

Abstract

Only recently, the RADIATION DETECTED RESONANCE IONIZATION SPECTROSCOPY (RADRIS) method was applied in the first laser spectroscopic investigation of nobelium which opened up possibilities for laser spectroscopy of the heaviest actinides towards super heavy elements. The application of the RADRIS technique to the heaviest actinide, lawrencium, the next element following nobelium, relies on the collection and efficient evaporation from a heated filament in the buffer gas cell. Different filament materials and geometries have been compared in a dedicated off-line test setup with respect to their desorption characteristics for the lighter homologue lutetium for the RADRIS technique. Desorption times, temperatures and the creation of surface-ion background have been studied dependent on the filament material and the operation temperature.

LISA ITN, 2020

For more information on the project, partners and contributors please see: lisa-itn.web.cern.ch

This Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action (MSCA) Innovative Training Network (ITN) receives funding from the European Union H2020 Framework Programme under grant agreement no. 861198. LISA will run from November 2019 to October 2023.

DELIVERY SLIP

	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	J. Warbinek	GSI	31/12/20
Edited by	S. Raeder	GSI	31/12/20
Reviewed by	M. Block [Task coordinator]	GSI	31/12/20
	I. Moore [WP coordinator]	JYU	
	I. Surname [Scientific coordinator]	[Short name]	
Approved by	I. Surname [Scientific coordinator] Steering Committee	[Short name]	dd/mm/yy

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION 4

2. FILAMENT REQUIREMENTS FOR THE RADRS TECHNIQUE 6

3. EXPERIMENT 7

 3.1. OFF-LINE SETUP7

 3.2. MEASUREMENT SCHEMES 8

4. RESULTS 9

 4.1. DESORPTION MEASUREMENTS9

 4.2. MECHANICAL STABILITY 10

5. CONCLUSION & OUTLOOK 12

6. REFERENCES 13

Executive Summary:

Laser spectroscopy of the heaviest actinides is in many ways a challenging task. Only recently, the development of the Radiation Detected Resonance Ionization Spectroscopy (RADRIS) allowed the first laser spectroscopic investigation of different nobelium isotopes at the GSI Helmholtz Centre for Heavy Ion Research in Darmstadt, Germany. This technique combines the collection and neutralization of recoil nuclei produced in fusion-evaporation reactions on a filament wire in a gas cell, followed by an efficient evaporation of these atoms by pulse heating the filament, laser ionization and eventually their detection. Turning to the heaviest actinide, lawrencium, demands the adaptation of the filament due to disadvantages of the tantalum filament previously used for nobelium evaporation.

Heating the filament to high temperatures, as required for thermal desorption, can lead to the creation of background ions from surface ionization dependent on the temperature, the ionization potential of the atoms and the work function of the filament. Utilizing the same tantalum filament for lawrencium produces orders of magnitude elevated surface-ion backgrounds due to the lower ionization potential of lawrencium. Suitable filament materials should have low work functions, low desorption temperatures and high melting points for stability in long-term operation.

An off-line setup dedicated for filament tests was developed to study the desorption characteristics of different filament types with lutetium, the iso-electronic homologue element of lawrencium. A lutetium vapour source serves for coating of the test filaments. Atoms evaporated from the filament are then resonantly ionized by a two-step laser excitation scheme and guided towards a detection chamber. With this setup, the relative fraction of surface ions as well as the desorption time constant can be examined as a function of their temperature dependence for different filament configurations.

Studying different refractory metals and coatings, hafnium proved to be the best choice with a sufficient longevity. Surface-ion contributions are suppressed by at least an order of magnitude compared to previously used tantalum filaments. A strong mechanical deformation of a thin hafnium-wire filament when applying the necessary desorption temperature for the RADRIS cycle was prevented, when 1 mm broad hafnium-strip filaments cut from hafnium foil were used.

Thus, a thin hafnium-strip filament suitable for the desorption of lutetium with a low surface ion background enables on-line laser spectroscopy of lawrencium applying the RADRIS technique for the search of first experimentally determined atomic levels.

1. INTRODUCTION

Laser spectroscopy is a powerful tool for the investigation of the atomic and nuclear structure of the actinide elements. Among these heavy, radioactive elements only uranium and thorium occur naturally, whereas all other actinides require a synthetic production in nuclear reactions [Blo20]. Studying these exotic elements by means of laser spectroscopy reveals their atomic structure, which is key in understanding the basic atomic and chemical behaviour of these elements. Revealing this structure is a stepping stone for the determination of nuclear properties like the nuclear spin, the nuclear charge radius and possible deformation of the nucleus

[Cam16, Che10]. Fundamental research on the actinides' structure supports the understanding of their chemical behaviour and enables new applications for nuclear power and in medical treatment methods.

In contrast to the lighter actinides, only very few experimental investigations on the atomic structure of the heaviest members in this series of elements have been performed until today. For their production, fusion-evaporation reactions at large accelerator facilities are indispensable, while low yields of only few ions per second or less and short half-lives of many of these nuclides demand highly efficient and sensitive detection methods immediate after production. Theoretical predictions on their atomic structure offer guidance for experiments [Eli15], but their limited accuracy requires large excitation-frequency ranges to be experimentally investigated.

For the first time, atomic transitions in the second heaviest actinide, nobelium (No, $Z=102$), were identified [Laa16] via the Radiation Detected Resonance Ionization Spectroscopy (RADRIS) method [Bac15, Lau16] at the GSI Helmholtz Centre for Heavy Ion Research in Darmstadt. Here, the nuclei were produced by complete fusion reactions of an intense ^{48}Ca beam with lead target nuclei. The fusion products were separated from the intense and high-energy projectile beam in the velocity filter SHIP [Mün79, Hof00] and guided into a gas cell filled with about 90 mbar argon buffer gas through a thin-foil entrance window. Inside the gas cell, the nuclei were stopped by collisions with the buffer gas atoms and were collected on a filament catcher accompanied by their neutralization. Subsequent pulse heating of the filament allowed the evaporation of the collected neutral atoms. Resonance ionization of these atoms in the gas phase by laser light in a two-step ionization scheme enabled the transport of created photo-ions towards an alpha-detector, enabling a selective detection via their unique alpha-decay energy. This RADRIS technique allowed recently not only to identify the first atomic levels in nobelium [Laa16] but also to determine its first ionization potential [Chh18] and, in combination with atomic calculations, to infer information on nuclear properties of the nobelium isotopes $^{252-254}\text{No}$ [Rae18].

For the heaviest actinide element, lawrencium (Lr, $Z=103$), experimentally no atomic transitions have been identified but only theoretical predictions exist to date [Bor07, Fri07, Dzu14], making it the last actinide element for which experimental data is not available. Successfully applying the RADRIS technique for lawrencium demands an efficient evaporation of neutral atoms from the filament used for capturing and neutralization. First tests with the iso-electronic homologue lutetium indicated an increased desorption temperature of Lr from the filament compared to No. Furthermore, lawrencium features a lower ionization potential compared to nobelium, which additionally elevates the surface-ion background, thus yielding a significantly reduced detection sensitivity. Requirements for suitable materials for an efficient evaporation and minimized surface-ion background are defined by the respective desorption enthalpy and a low filament work function, respectively. Therefore, a tailor-made measurement chamber served to compare these properties for different filament types and materials based on the desorption of lutetium. This provided insight into the applicability of the RADRIS technique in upcoming experiments on lawrencium.

2. FILAMENT REQUIREMENTS FOR THE RADRS TECHNIQUE

Suitable filament materials and geometries are crucial for the required high overall efficiency in the RADRS measurement scheme. During one heating pulse, a complete evaporation of the recoils collected on the filament must be ensured. While higher temperatures decrease the desorption time, moderate temperatures are beneficial as they extend the filament lifetime leading to an uninterrupted series of measurement cycles. In addition, turbulences in the buffer gas that adversely affect the efficiency of the technique are reduced at lower temperatures. More importantly, lower evaporation temperatures reduce the signal contribution of laser-independent background ions created by the non-resonant surface-ionization process on the hot filament. This surface-ion production can additionally be influenced by the work function of the filament material, which determines the energy needed for an electron to leave the surface. Surface ionization is reduced when this work function is much lower than the ionization potential (IP) of the atom of interest.

The Saha-Langmuir equation describes the relative count rate of surface ions n_+ to the rate of evaporated neutral atoms n_0 dependent on the degeneracies of the ionic g_+ and atomic states g_0 as

$$\frac{n_+}{n_0} = \frac{g_+}{g_0} e^{-\left(\frac{E_{IP}-\Phi}{k_B T}\right)}, \quad (1)$$

where E_{IP} is the ionization potential of the collected atoms, Φ is the work function of the filament material, k_B is the Boltzmann constant and T the filament temperature. This relative surface-ion count rate for different temperatures is shown in Fig. 1. in dependence on $E_{IP} - \Phi$.

Fig. 1 Calculated surface-ion rate relative to the rate of released neutral atoms versus difference of the ionization potential of the atoms and the filament work function. Shown are surface-ion rates for three different filament temperatures. A dashed line marks the ionization potential to work function difference of No atoms on a Ta filament, the dashed-dotted line shows Lr on a Hf filament and the dotted line Lr on a Ta filament.

In the previous experiments for the study of No isotopes, a 125 μm thick tantalum wire was used for collection and desorption. This combination worked very well as temperatures of only 1100°C were required for a complete desorption with a heat-pulse duration of 300 ms. Moreover, the work function $\Phi_{\text{Ta}}=4.22$ eV of tantalum [Mic77] in conjunction with an IP of $E_{IP}(\text{No})=6.33$ eV for nobelium [Chh18] led to a negligible contribution from surface ions, enabling very sensitive scanning for atomic transitions for this element. For the next heavier element, lawrencium (Lr, $Z=103$), a first IP with $E_{IP}(\text{Lr})=4.96$ eV was experimentally determined by a surface-ionization technique [Sat15, Sat18]. In addition, the desorption is hampered as the desorption enthalpy for Lr from Ta was calculated only recently to be about 600 kJ/mol [Per20], which is significantly larger compared to the 250 kJ/mol measured for the desorption of No from Ta [Laa14]. This leads

to substantially increased desorption temperatures. The reason for this behaviour results from the influence of the d- and p-electrons in the atomic shell of Lr. While the atomic shell of nobelium features a $[\text{Rn}]7s^2f^{14}$ configuration with a completely closed s- and f-shell configuration, the atomic ground state of Lr is predicted to be $[\text{Rn}]7s^2f^{14}7p_{1/2}$. The $p_{1/2}$ electron results in a larger polarizability of the atomic shell leading to an increased adsorption. This behaviour is typical for the transition metals (the next element and first transactinide element rutherfordium (Rf, $Z=104$) belongs to this group) and is often referred to as refractory behaviour describing the fact that these elements feature high melting and boiling temperatures and therefore low vapour pressures.

As a consequence, the desorption behaviour and the surface-ion behaviour need to be studied in advance of the level search to identify the best-suited filament material. However, this is not feasible in on-line experiments on Lr due to several challenges. Instead, off-line measurements on the homologue element, lutetium (Lu, $Z=71$), were performed for these tests. Lutetium features a similar electron configuration and a similar chemical behaviour: its ionization potential $E_{\text{IP}}(\text{Lu})= 5.42$ eV [Mae89] is slightly higher than the IP of Lr, while its desorption enthalpy is 618 kJ/mol [Per20] and therefore only slightly larger.

In summary, a filament optimized for the Lr collection and evaporation should have a low work function, a low desorption temperature for Lr and a high melting point to ensure stability and reduced mechanical deformation of the filament. A stable performance under these high-temperature heat pulses is expected for refractory metals such as, e.g., Hf, W, Th besides the previously applied Ta. Different filament materials and geometries were tested in an off-line setup using a Lu vapour source to find a suitable option for Lr.

3. EXPERIMENT

3.1. OFF-LINE SETUP

For the filament studies, a dedicated off-line test chamber was utilized as shown in Fig. 2. This chamber consists of separate sections for the preparation with resonant laser ionization and the ion detection. These two sections are connected via ion-guiding optics including a quadrupole mass filter (QMF) for a mass identification of the respective ions. The preparation chamber contains a lutetium vapour source consisting of a piece of thin Lu foil embedded in a folded strip of tantalum foil and the filament to be tested. Resistive heating of the tantalum-source strip leads to slow evaporation of neutral lutetium and consequent coating of the filament positioned above the vapour source. The filament itself is placed in an aluminium cage with entrance holes for the vapour and laser beams to ensure an extraction of the subsequently produced photo-ions by defined electrostatic potentials. With this Lu coating of a filament, the collection and evaporation cycle can be simulated analogous to the on-line RADRIS technique [Lau16]. The entire setup is placed in a vacuum chamber at a pressure of about 10^{-7} mbar, while windows which are transmissive for the required UV laser wavelengths enclose the sides of the preparation chamber to enable unperturbed laser illumination of evaporated Lu atoms. In addition, the temperature of the filament is monitored using an adjustable pyrometer (Luma-Sense Tech., Impac IS 6 Advance) outside the chamber through one of the windows. A detailed description of the preparation chamber can be found in [Mur20]. Inside the detection chamber, a channel electron multiplier (CEM, KBL25RS, Dr. Sjuts Optotechnik GmbH) allows single-particle detection of ions transmitted through the QMF. The QMF is optimized for ion transmission and therefore operated in a low-resolution mode with a width of a few atomic mass units at a mass of 180 u.

Fig. 2 Off-line setup for filament tests. The preparation chamber on the left contains the test filament with backplate and cage electrode for ion guiding. The vapour source beneath the filament cage evaporates Lu atoms for the desorption measurements. An Einzel lens and a QMF serve for ion guidance, mass selection and focussing to the CEM in the detection chamber.

Due to the heating of the filament, surface contaminants are evaporated as neutral species but also as surface ions as described by the Saha-Langmuir equation in (1). The ion fraction, which can be directly guided to the CEM and consequently be detected, consists of surface ions from the lutetium coating, but also of ions from lutetium oxides and alkaline metals. Thus, the QMF is crucial for unambiguously identifying the Lu-ion signal by suppressing contaminations of other masses. The neutral fraction of Lu atoms released from the filament can be selectively probed by resonance ionization laser spectroscopy [Let87, Mur20]. During these experiments, the resonant ionization of the Lu atoms is realized via a two-step laser ionization scheme. The first step leads to population of the $5d6s(^3D)6p\ ^2D^{\circ}_{3/2}$ first excited state at $22\ 124.8\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ [Kra20] from the $5d6s^2\ ^2D_{3/2}$ ground state, the second step with a wavenumber of $25\ 566.7\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ matches the transition from the first excited to an auto-ionizing state at a total excitation energy of about $47\ 691.5\ \text{cm}^{-1}$. Both excitation steps are provided by dye lasers pumped by the same Xe:Cl excimer laser at 308 nm and are transported via optical fibres towards the vacuum chamber. For optimum resonance ionization, the spatial overlap of both lasers is controlled via a multi-fibre coupler in front of the transmissive window of the chamber. Due to operation of the excimer laser system at 100 Hz, a gated detection of ions registered at the CEM triggered by the laser allows for an increased sensitivity of laser-produced ions with respect to surface-ion background. However, this low repetition rate reduces the duty cycle as the flight time through the laser-interaction region of the thermal evaporated atoms with velocities as high as 1000 m/s is on the order of tens of microseconds.

The measurement cycle for tests of filaments in the off-line chamber starts with coating of the filament with Lu from the vapour source. After a given coating time, the heating of the source is stopped and the filament itself resistively pulse heated to a certain temperature. The Lu coating on the surface is evaporated, the laser pulses arranged accordingly to resonantly ionize the atoms. Count rates of created ions are recorded with and without laser impact to determine surface-ion creation and their signal contribution for the respective filament type.

3.2. MEASUREMENT SCHEMES

The described off-line setup offers the possibility for testing different filament characteristics. For these investigations, different measurement schemes can be applied as shown in the sketch of the sequences used in the different schemes in Fig. 3. First, the vapour source can be used to coat the filament when heated at a constant current. The deposited species can be desorbed from the filament surface by heating the filament either at a constant temperature or using, analogue to the on-line measurement, pulse heating. The released ions can be monitored with the CEM and the neutral fraction can be probed after resonant laser ionization

also with the CEM. A constant heating of the filament enables monitoring the ion signal over time. A determination of the decay constant of this exponential decrease, the desorption time constant, can thus be examined with respect to its temperature dependence for different filament choices. The remainder of surface contaminants on the filament after a short heat pulse can be probed by monitoring the remaining ion signal when a second constant heating current is applied for a rather long-lasting desorption. In comparison to the fast signal from the short heat pulses, measuring the slow signal of the full depletion is less dependent on data-acquisition limitations that are due to the limited resolution of the data recording in case of close signals. Thus, it can give a measure of the surface-ion count rate released during the previous heat pulse. This second measurement scheme is similar to the measurements performed in the on-line spectroscopy of No, where the fraction of nobelium remaining on the filament after a heat pulse was determined by its characteristic radioactive decay [Laa14]. Nevertheless, it should be noted that the signals can only be compared in a relative manner, as the total detection efficiencies for, e.g., surface ions and laser ions, respectively, are quite different due to a different acceptance of the ion-transport system and the limited duty cycle of the laser ionization. Therefore, the absolute surface ionization efficiency cannot be probed, while the surface-ion fraction can be compared for different filament temperatures and materials, which is the main scope of the investigations.

Beside filament tests, this off-line chamber also enables laser spectroscopic investigations of the provided vapour source sample. Without heating the filament, detected ions are purely laser related and created by resonance ionization. Scanning the second laser step, auto-ionizing states can be searched, which can be addressed in the RADRIS method. Addressing known excited states of short lifetimes by scanning the first excitation step can also give a measure of the laser linewidth.

Figure 3: Two different measurements schemes for the investigation of filaments in the off-line setup. The upper scheme sketches the measurement of the desorption time for different temperatures of the filament and the possibility to measure the change in the ratio of surface ions to laser ions. The lower scheme sketches the measurement of the pulse heating tests for the on-line cycle. The second measurement heating pulse allows to reliably measure the remaining material on the filament as the fast signal during the pulse desorption exceeds the dead time of the data acquisition.

4. RESULTS

4.1. DESORPTION MEASUREMENTS

A typical result of a desorption measurement is shown Fig. 4 (left). During the first part of the graph, the signal obtained with laser ionization is shown, while the second part is a repetition of the measurement without laser irradiation. The first strong and about 20-s-long signal is obtained during the filament coating from the vapour source. This signal also allows monitoring the coating and the quality of the vapour source. Nevertheless, it should be mentioned that the signal during coating already results in dead time of the data

acquisition, therefore a full quantitative analysis is impossible. After coating, the filament is heated, in this measurement to a temperature of about 1820 K. The signal from the filament is decaying with a time constant of about 1 s. In the second part of the cycle, the coating is repeated, the laser irradiation is turned off and the signal monitored accordingly. Here, the signal during coating is significantly reduced, but still some surface ions from the evaporated Lu are detected. In addition, the signal from surface ionization during the filament heating is reduced compared to the measurement with resonant laser ionization. Although the reduction in this measurement appears to be only by a factor of 2.5, it has to be noted that the duty cycle of the laser ionization reduces the laser-induced signal by a factor of about 100. This measurement can be performed for different filament temperatures and for different filament materials.

A result of the most promising materials is shown in the right panel of Fig. 4. Here, a comparison of the performance of tantalum and hafnium filaments is shown. Both materials have a comparable desorption behaviour as already discussed in Sec. 2, the surface ionization of tantalum is more than one order of magnitude higher compared to hafnium. Nevertheless, temperatures well above 1800 K are required for a full desorption during a short heating pulse as applied in the on-line experiments.

A third filament type which was investigated was a thoriated tungsten wire. For this, a thin carbon layer was sputter-coated to avoid oxygen poisoning of the filament in the vacuum chamber, which degrades the expected low work function behaviour of the thorium at the surface. More details are discussed in [Mur20]. Although this filament showed a lower desorption temperature and superior surface-ion suppression, the longevity of the filament did not match the requirement in an on-line experiment, in which about 3000 heating pulses are expected per day. The thoriated filament lasted only a few hundred cycles at the required desorption temperatures before the carbon coating vanished and a large surface-ion signal appeared, rendering this filament unsuitable for on-line usage. In addition, other coatings on tungsten filaments were tested with low-work-function materials featuring a high melting point (Y, LaB₆, WC, HfC). However, these materials had desorption temperatures exceeding the thermal stability of the coating and where thus not even applicable for test purposes. Finally, hafnium proved to be the most suitable material despite the disadvantage of a remaining surface-ion contribution and a reduced mechanical stability at higher temperatures due to an increased ductility.

Figure 4: The left graph shows a typical desorption measurement with two coating cycles where one was obtained with resonant laser ionization and the second one without. The right graph shows the obtained decay constants for different filament temperatures and different filament materials.

4.2. MECHANICAL STABILITY

Two types of the promising Hf filament configurations were tested for their mechanical stability when resistively heated to very high temperatures. A 4 cm long piece of a 125 μm thin Hf wire was connected to the upper test position electrodes in the off-line setup, while a 1 mm wide Hf-foil strip with a thickness of

25 μm of the same length was connected to the lower test position as shown in Fig. 5. For further stability, the ends of the Hf-strip filament were turned outwards which induced a minor upwards bend in the filament. Both filaments were heated by external current supplies and the temperatures of both were measured. The constant heating of both filaments was performed increasing the temperature in equal steps. To reach the same temperature as for the wire, about twice the heating current was necessary for the Hf strip, which is consistent with the increased geometrical cross section and the resulting reduced resistance of the strip geometry. For temperatures above 1200 K, the Hf wire started to bend downwards while no deformation was observed on the strip. For even higher temperatures, the deformation of the wire continued until a 90° tilt was reached. This maximum bend turned out to be a stable deformation as no further elongation of the filament was observed. At a desorption temperature of about 2100 K for the Lr RADRS cycle, the wire was at the maximum tilt while for the strip only a slight trend downwards was observed. Increasing the heating current even more resulted in burning and thus destruction of the filament wire; the strip however sustained these higher temperatures. In previous tests, the longevity of the Hf strip extended over a series of about 3600 heating pulses exceeding the expected number of pulses in a measurement campaign day by about 20% before breaking [Mur20]. However, a reduction in the Hf-filament lifetime is expected due to the creation of Hf-oxide layers in case of an extended exposure of the filament to air.

Figure 5: Thin hafnium filament wire (125 μm) in upper test position and 1mm hafnium strip in lower test position. For better comparison, both filaments have a length of 4 cm. On the left, both initial filaments are shown before heating. After continuously, resistively heating both to about 2100 K, the Hf wire experienced a maximum deformation of a 90° bend downwards. The Hf strip showed only a minor bend.

5. CONCLUSION & OUTLOOK

An off-line setup capable of realizing specific measurement schemes was used to test different refractory metals for their suitability as filaments applying the RADRIS technique for laser spectroscopy of lawrencium. The filaments were compared based on an efficient desorption of lutetium, the lighter homologue of Lr. A Hf strip from commercially available thin Hf foil was proven to be the most reliable and stable filament among the variety of materials investigated. Hafnium offers a low work function reducing surface-ion rates by more than one order of magnitude compared to the use of Ta. The low desorption temperature additionally minimizes turbulences in the buffer gas close to the filament. The strip design reduces the mechanical deformation of the Hf filament at the required temperature and enables to maintain the high total efficiency of the technique.

Hf-strip filaments offer an efficient desorption of Lr and thus, enable the performance of laser spectroscopy with the RADRIS technique. In upcoming on-line experiments on Lr, the Hf-strip filament type will be used. After a first successful identification of atomic states, the in-gas-jet spectroscopy technique will be implemented, utilizing this filament to perform hyperfine spectroscopy of Lr.

6. REFERENCES

JOURNAL ARTICLES:

[Bac15] Backe, H. et al. (2015) Prospects for laser spectroscopy, ion chemistry and mobility measurements of superheavy elements in buffer-gas traps, *Nuclear Physics A*, 944, pp 492-517.

[Blo20] Block, M. et al. (2020) Recent progress in laser spectroscopy of the actinides, *Progress in Particle and Nuclear Physics*, 116, 103834.

[Bor07] Borschevsky, A. et al. (2007) Transition energies of atomic lawrencium, *The European Physical Journal D*, 45, 115-119.

[Cam16] Campbell, P. et al. (2016) Laser spectroscopy for nuclear structure physics, *Progress in Particle and Nuclear Physics*, 86, pp 127-180.

[Che10] Cheal, B. and Flanagan, K.T. (2010) Progress in laser spectroscopy at radioactive ion beam facilities, *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics*, 37(11), 113101.

[Chh18] Chhetri, P. et al. (2018) Precision measurement of the first ionization potential of nobelium, *Physical Review Letters*, 120(26), 263003.

[Dzu14] Dzuba, V.A. et al. (2014) Atomic properties of superheavy elements No, Lr, and Rf, *Physical Review A*, 90(1), 012504.

[Eli15] Eliav, E. et al. (2015) Electronic structure theory of the superheavy elements, *Nuclear Physics A*, 944, pp 518-550.

[Fri07] Fritzsche, S. et al. (2007) The low-lying level structure of atomic lawrencium ($Z=103$): energies and absorption rates, *The European Physical Journal D*, 45, pp 107-113.

[Hof00] Hofmann, S. and Münzenberg, G. (2000) The discovery of the heaviest elements, *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 72(3), 733.

[Laa14] Laatiaoui, M. et al. (2014) On laser spectroscopy of the element nobelium ($Z=102$), *The European Physical Journal D*, 68, 71.

[Laa16] Laatiaoui, M. et al. (2016) Atom-at-a-time laser resonance ionization spectroscopy of nobelium, *Nature*, 538, pp 495-498.

[Lau16] Lautenschläger, F. et al. (2016) Developments for resonance ionization laser spectroscopy of the heaviest elements at SHIP, *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 383, pp 115-122.

[Mae89] Maeda, H. et al. (1989) Highly excited even Rydberg series of Lu I studied by two-step laser photoionisation spectroscopy, *Journal of Physics B: Atomic, Molecular and Optical Physics*, 22, pp L511-L516.

[Mic77] Michaelson, H.B. (1977) The work function of the elements and its periodicity, *Journal of Applied Physics*, 48, pp 4729-4733.

[Mün79] Münzenberg, G. et al. (1979) The velocity filter SHIP, a separator of unslowed heavy ion fusion products, *Nuclear Instruments and Methods*, 161(1), pp 65-82.

[Per20] Pershina, V. (2020) Relativistic effects on the properties of Lr: a periodic DFT study of the adsorption of Lr on surfaces of Ta in comparison with Lu and Tl, *Inorganic Chemistry*, 59, pp 5490-5496.

[Rae18] Raeder, S. et al. (2018) Probing sizes and shapes of nobelium isotopes by laser spectroscopy, *Physical Review Letters*, 120(23), 232503.

[Sat15] Sato, T.K. et al. (2015) Measurement of the first ionization potential of lawrencium, element 103, *Nature*, 520, pp 209-211.

[Sat18] Sato, T.K. et al. (2018) First ionization potentials of Fm, Md, No, and Lr: verification of filling-up of 5f electrons and confirmation of the actinide series, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 140, pp 14609-14613.

CONFERENCE PAPERS:

[Mur20] Murböck, T. et al. (2020) Filament studies for laser spectroscopy on lawrencium, *Hyperfine Interactions*, 241, pp 1-9.

BOOKS:

[Let87] Letokhov, V.S. (1987) *Laser photoionization spectroscopy*, Academic Press INC.

Formatted: Finnish

Formatted: Finnish

Formatted: Finnish

Formatted: Finnish

Formatted: Finnish

WORLD WIDE WEB DOCUMENTS:

[Kra20] Kramida, A. et al. (2020) *Nist atomic spectra database* (version 5.8) [online]. Available from: https://physics.nist.gov/PhysRefData/ASD/lines_form.html [Accessed 31 December 2020].

ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
CEM	Channel Electron Multiplier
IP	Ionization Potential
QMF	Quadrupole Mass Filter
RADRES	Radiation Detected Resonance Ionization Spectroscopy
SHIP	Separator for Heavy Ion reaction Products
UV	Ultraviolet